

Visualization of the Multiverse – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

This paper will present a visual model for the structure of the Multiverse based on the main equation of the 8 theory, the coupling constants series and the recent ideas and insights, in particular universe packets. Analysis of the phenomena of singularity and the inflation becomes more vivid and coherent using that model alongside the phenomena of time invariant acceleration from extremum curvature on the Lorentz manifold; those will be analyzed as well in the assay.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.12)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.13)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.14)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.15)$$

This is of course a simplistic model, we need infinite liars attached to each other, and here there are only two. Each liar contains areas of extremum curvatures that are noticeable at the manifold at large scale. Those areas are interacting or influenced by similar areas at distinct manifolds, causing a mutual pressure outward on the matrix of each manifold, the result is an accelerating manifold in which the areas of extremum curvatures retain their nature. There are infinite amount of manifolds wrappings or universe packets, similar to wave packets structure in physics.

Imagine that there is thin liar of super space, or topological space between of each two liars or two distinct manifolds, that is the topological space of $\partial g/\partial t = 0$ if one is correct. In other words, pure energy, the separating space is the same for all manifolds; we can say that these manifolds are topologically invariant. The configuration of the manifold matter distribution is of course different in each manifold, the stage of development is unique to each manifold, but the interactions or bosonic fields and the same rules for all manifolds. The laws are invariant, but the stage and configuration is different.

Cosmological inflation is due to the shift from compressed manifolds, highly dense in which there is net curvature, yielding an outward acceleration by the packet of universes wrapping the manifold. Imagine the sheer pressure by an infinite amount of universes on a highly dense not so flat manifold, and inflation at the scale of our own manifold is then becomes reasonable. According to this model, each manifold becomes more and more flat over time; the distance between each point of extremum curvature gets bigger, in agreement with what we know about our own manifold. Another simplistic visual model, which describe liars of manifolds stacking. Each manifold is a parallel wrapping of its succeeding.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)